

Mechanical Behaviors of Aluminum Alloys Reinforced with B and SiC Filaments, and Properties of B-Al Alloy Composite as a High Speed Rotor Cylinder

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ABSTRACT

B- and SiC-reinforced-aluminum alloy composites were consolidated under diffusion bonding conditions without using the vacuum bagging process. Filaments with tungsten or carbon substrates were used.

The strengths of B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites in the direction of reinforcement were about 85% and 75% of the values calculated by the rule of mixtures, respectively, while the tensile moduli in the same direction coincided rather well with the predicted values for both materials. Typical strength and tensile modulus of B-aluminum alloy with 50% volume fraction of B filament were about 1.50 GN/m² and 250 GN/m² respectively.

The ratio of the fatigue strength to the monotonic strength for B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composite was large in contrast with the small ratio for an aluminum alloy reinforced with SUS304 stainless steel filament.

A high speed rotor made out of a B-aluminum alloy composite cylinder 200 mm in diameter and 300 mm in length survived the circumferential speed of 675 m/s (1070 rps).

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber reinforced metals or metal matrix composites are characterized by efficient mechanical properties such as high shearing strength and high tensile and shearing moduli, and by heat resistant properties, compared with fiber reinforced plastics. Metal matrix composites also surpasses metals with respect to specific strength and modulus.

On the other hand, metal matrix composite materials have some drawbacks. Not only the filament for metal matrix composite production is generally expensive, but it costs a great deal to process metal matrix composites, because consolidation of the metal matrix composites is usually performed under high pressures and high temperatures in a vacuum atmosphere, and needs laborious work.

In this study B- and SiC-aluminum composites were consolidated without using the vacuum bagging process. No mono-tape and mono-sheet of B- or SiC-aluminum alloy were used. Metal matrix composite cylinders reinforced mainly in the hoop direction were manufactured without the aid of any kind of autoclave.

Tensile monotonic tests on coupon specimens and cylinders of metal matrix composites were conducted to investigate mechanical properties under tensile stress. The composite cylinders were broken under hoop stress generated by

pressing a rubber disk set inside the cylinders. Tensile fatigue tests were also conducted on coupon specimens. The influence of differences in the matrix metal, the filament substrate and the filament diameter on monotonic and fatigue properties of B- and SiC-aluminum composites were investigated through these experiments.

High speed rotors which could be used as gravity centrifuges were fabricated using B-aluminum composite cylinders. Rotating tests on the composite rotor were conducted to confirm durability and stability of the metal matrix composite as a high speed rotor cylinder. Rotating characteristics of the metal matrix composite rotor were investigated.

2. REINFORCING FILAMENT, MATRIX METAL, WAY OF CONSOLIDATION, TESTING METHOD

2.1 Reinforcing filaments and matrix metals

Reinforcing filaments used were B and SiC monofilaments which have carbon or tungsten substrates. The monofilament was adopted because it is easy to avoid direct contact of filaments to the neighboring ones and to place matrix metal uniformly around the filaments when the monofilament is used. The filament diameters were 102 and 142 μm . Monofilaments of stainless steels SUS304 and SUS316 with the diameters of 80 and 70 μm respectively were also used for helical winding to raise axial strength of metal matrix composite cylinders. Flexible stainless steel filaments were judged suitable to avoid fatal breakdown during helical winding. Small diameters were chosen for the stainless steel filaments to make the helix layers thin, because the helix layer had little contribution to the hoop strength of the metal matrix composite cylinder. Specification of the filaments used are listed in Table 1.

Aluminum alloys were used as metal matrix to make the metal matrix composite cylinder light, because higher specific strength is required for high speed rotor

Table 1. Physical and mechanical properties of reinforcing filaments used.

Filament	Diameter (μm)	Specific gravity	Tensile strength (GN/m^2)	Tensile modulus (GN/m^2)
B/W	102	2.57	3.43	402
"	142	2.49	3.53	402
B/C	142	2.27	3.24	382
SiC/W	142	3.18	3.14	431
SiC/C	142	2.90	3.92	441
SUS 304	80	8.03	1.57	186
SUS 316	70	8.03	1.57	186

cylinders. Pure aluminum was discarded because of low monotonic and fatigue strengths of the B- pure aluminum composite as shown in Fig.1. 2024 and 6061 aluminum alloy foils 70 and 50 μm thick were adopted to form the matrix of the metal matrix composites.

2.1 The way of consolidation

Metal matrix composite plates were consolidated with a hot press. B- and SiC-aluminum alloy preforms made with the aid of a filament winder were cut and stacked to form desired metal matrix composite plates.

Fig. 1. Monotonic and fatigue test results on reinforced pure aluminum.

Metal matrix composite cylinders were processed with a device shown in Fig. 2. Filament and matrix foil layers alternately formed on a mandrel, used also as the inner die, using a filament winder, were covered with a couple of radially split steel liners, and set inside the outer die, and put into an electric furnace to apply heat. High pressure necessary for consolidation was generated by constraining thermal expansion of the inner die made of SUS316 stainless steel with the outer die made of graphite circumferentially wound on the outside with dry carbon fibers and insulated with asbestos rope layers and additionally protected with a layer of asbestos-dispersed alumina cement. Metal matrix composite cylinders were basically reinforced in the hoop direction, while some of them were also reinforced with helically wound B/W or SUS filament.

The consolidating temperature and pressure were $530 \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ and around 35 MPa respectively. Consolidating time chosen was 30 minutes. Consolidation was carried out in the ambient atmosphere without using any kind of vacuum bagging. Tensile forces given to the filament at the time of winding were 7.5N and 1.5N for hoop and helix windings respectively. The filaments in the hoop layers were fixed with acrylic resin Aron S1060, while the filaments in the helix layers were daubed with aluminum paste which contained the same kind of aluminum alloy powder as aluminum foil used for matrix and the acrylic resin dissolved with Solvesso 151. Filament breakdown, direct mutual contact of filaments and void formation at the filament crossings in the helix layer were prevented by the aluminum paste daubing.

MgO powder sprayed over the surfaces of the dies and liners served as an anti-sticking agent.

Acrylic resin Aron S1060 vaporized at the temperature above 150°C , and did not become any hindrance to solidification of the metal matrix composite.

Surfaces of B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composite plates and cylinders were chemically polished in an alkaline liquid (MIL-D26549) and neutralized with nitric acid, and finally washed in water.

2.3 Test methods

Monotonic tensile tests and pulsating tension fatigue tests were carried out on coupon specimens. The longitudinal coupon specimens were 1 to 1.7 mm thick, 10 mm wide and 30 to 50 mm in gage length, while the off-axis coupon specimens were 0.7 to 1.6 mm thick, 20 or 30 mm wide, and 50 mm in gage length. Aluminum alloy doublers were bonded on each surface at both ends of the specimens. Tensile modulus was calculated from the inclination of a stress-strain curve recorded with the aid of strain gages cemented on both sides of the specimen. The speed of load application was 8.3 mm/s for monotonic tensile tests. Pulsating fatigue tests were conducted with a servo-controlled hydraulic apparatus at the speed of 10 Hz.

The metal matrix composite cylinders were circumferentially stressed by pressing the rubber disk set

Fig. 2. Setup to consolidate filament-reinforced-metal cylinders.

Fig. 3. Setup to evaluate mechanical properties of MMC cylinders. (unit: mm)

inside the cylinders as shown in Fig.3. Tested cylinders were about 0.5 mm thick, about 200 mm in inside diameter and 105 mm in length. The thickness was 0.65 to 0.7 mm in case of the cylinders with an additional helix layer. Interfaces between the cylinder and the rubber disk and between the rubber disk and the steel press disks were lubricated with MoS₂ to restrain the frictional effect. Hoop stress generated in the cylinder were estimated by subtracting deformation resistance of the rubber disk from the press load.

3 MECHANICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF FILAMENT REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

3.1 Monotonic tensile test results

Longitudinal strengths of B-aluminum composites are plotted versus the volumetric fraction of the filament (V_f) in Fig.4. Scatter band of the longitudinal strength was as large as seen in the case of ordinary fiber-reinforced plastic composites. The longitudinal strength increased linearly with the increase in V_f value, and was about 85% of the values estimated with the rule of mixtures. The differences of the filament diameter and filament substrate gave little effect to the room temperature strength of the B-aluminum composite under monotonic tension. Aluminum alloys 2024 and 6061 as composite matrix seemed to make little difference in the longitudinal strength. In Fig.4 the results on B-aluminum composite cylinders were also plotted. Hoop strengths of B-aluminum composite cylinders coincided rather well with those for B-aluminum coupon specimens, and were relatively higher than the strengths of CFRP cylinders plotted in the figure as a reference.

Monotonic tensile test results on SiC-aluminum alloy composite are illustrated in Fig.5. As in the case of B-aluminum composites, the strength of SiC-aluminum coupon specimens also increases with the V_f value. The monotonic tensile strength was about 75% of the estimate values calculated with the rule of mixtures. This value is a little smaller than for B-aluminum composites. The smaller value seemed due to the residual tensile stress existent at the surface of SiC filament which helped the filament to crack at the lower tensile stress¹⁾, and also due to smoothness of SiC filament surface or low wettability with aluminum ma-

Fig. 4. Relationship between tensile strength and volume fraction of filament (B-AL).

Fig. 5. Relationship between tensile strength and volume fraction of filament (SiC-AL).

trix which caused weak bonding between the filament and the matrix metal. It was possible, however, to produce cylinders which had hoop strength more the 1 GM/m² and were comparable to CFRP cylinders.

Longitudinal tensile moduli for B- and SiC-AL6061 composites are given in Figs. 6 and 7. Longitudinal tensile moduli coincided with the predicted values calculated with the rule of mixtures for both of the composite materials. The value of tensile modulus for composite coupon specimens was realized in composite cylinders as in the case of the tensile strength. The value of tensile modulus at 50% volumetric fraction of filament seemed more than that of steels.

In Fig. 8 is given the change in tensile strength with filament orientation. A solid, a dashed and a dash-dot lines indicate criterions for tensile fractures in planes perpendicular to the filaments, parallel to the filaments and for shear fracture along the filament-matrix interfaces respectively. F_L and F_T were taken as the mean values of longitudinal and transverse tensile strengths respectively. F_{LT} was assumed to be one half of the tensile strength of the matrix metal. Experimental results took the values between the theoretical values predicted by shear fracture along the filaments and the transverse tensile fracture at filament orientations less than 0.35 rad (20 degrees), while the experimental results tended to the values predicted by the tensile fracture in the transverse direction beyond 0.35 rad (20 degrees). Transverse strengths for specimens with V_f of 22% are also plotted in Fig. 8. It seemed that favorable specimen preparation would bring about the same transverse strength as the inherent tensile strength of the matrix aluminum alloy.

Fig. 9 shows comparison between longitudinal and transverse tensile moduli of B-aluminum composite coupon specimens. Transverse tensile modulus seemed larger than the tensile modulus of the matrix metal.

Poisson's ratios in longitudinal and transverse directions are given in Fig. 10. Longitudinal Poisson's ratio ν_{LT} ($\theta=0^\circ$) was 0.29, a little smaller than that for aluminum alloy matrix, and the transverse Poisson's ratio ν_{TL} ($\theta=90^\circ$) was 0.06 which was close to the value predicted by the reciprocal theorem using ν_{LT} and the tensile modulus shown in Fig. 9.

The influence of heat treatment on transverse mechanical characteristics of B-AL6061 composite is shown in Table 2. Within the scope of this experiment, T6 treatment on B-AL6061 composite did not seem to give distinct improvement in

Fig. 6. Relationship between tensile modulus and volume fraction of filament (B-AL).

Fig. 7. Relationship between tensile modulus and volume fraction of filament (SiC-AL).

Fig. 8. Change in tensile strength with filament orientation (B-AL).

Fig. 9. Change in tensile modulus with filament orientation (B-AL).

Fig. 10. Poisson's ratio for longitudinal and transverse specimens (B-AL).

transverse tensile strength and modulus. On the other hand, it should be kept in mind that heat treatment might bring about filament degradation and give adverse effects on longitudinal mechanical characteristics.

3.2 Fatigue test results

Fatigue test results on B- and SiC-aluminum composites under pulsating tension are given in Figs. 11 and 12 respectively. Fatigue strengths for B-aluminum composites which had 2024 and 6061 matrices seemed to coincide well with each other as seen in the monotonic tensile results (Fig.4). Fatigue strength under pulsating tension was relatively high compared with monotonic tensile strength for both B- and SiC-aluminum composites in contrast with the relatively lower fatigue strength in ordinary metals.*1

Table 2. Effect of heat treatment on transverse tensile properties of 6061 reinforced with 102 μm B/W filament.

V _f (%)	Heat treatment	Tensile strength (MN/m ²)	Tensile modulus (GN/m ²)
22	F	104	61.8
	T 6	109	56.9
22	F	95	59.8
	T 6	129	58.8

Fatigue strength of SUS304-AL6061 composite under pulsating tension is shown

*1 Not only monotonic tensile strength but tensile fatigue strength was low in SiC-AL6061 composite. This was judged due to inferior filament quality caused by uneven cross section, surface contamination and unsatisfactory surface finish of the SiC/W filament supplied at the beginning. Improvement in characteristics of the filament supplied later led to the increase in tensile strength of the SiC-AL6061 composite cylinder as seen in Fig.5. Improvement in fatigue strength would also be expected for the metal matrix composite produced using the improved filament.

in Fig.13 to compare with the results on B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites. As seen in the figure, high monotonic strength does not necessarily mean high fatigue strength in the case of metal filament reinforced metal matrix composites.

As has been stated already, B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites consolidated in the ambient atmosphere without using the vacuum bagging process had excellent mechanical properties. The consolidation process which applied the difference of thermal expansion of the inner and the outer dies to generate high pressure necessary for consolidation of metal matrix composite was successfully used to produce high strength metal matrix composite cylinders reinforced mainly in the hoop direction.

4 APPLICATION OF B-AL6061 COMPOSITE CYLINDER TO HIGH SPEED ROTOR

High speed rotors as shown in Fig.14 were fabricated using circumferentially reinforced B-AL6061 composite cylinders 200 mm in inside diameter. End disks connected with shafts, after having been cooled down in liquid nitrogen, were shrinkage fitted into composite cylinders. The amount of interference chosen was 350 μ m. The disks had the configuration which could cancel the diametral increase of the composite cylinder due to hoop stress induced by rotation and could prevent from variation in interference. Mass balancing was conducted on the outer surfaces near the circumference of both disks.

The composite rotor was mo-

(a) $l=300$

(b) $l=740$

Fig. 14. High speed rotors ($D=\phi 200$) (B-AL). (unit:mm)

Fig. 11. Fatigue test result (B-AL).

Fig. 12. Fatigue test result (SiC-AL).

Fig. 13. Fatigue test result (SUS304-AL).

tor-driven in a vertical position in a vacuum higher than 0.133 Pa. The composite rotor cylinder of which was 300 mm in length survived the circumferential speed of 675 m/s (1070 rps). In Fig.15 are given displacement variations of the upper and the lower shafts measured at the bearings at 675 m/s (1070 rps). The estimated hoop stress generated in the rotor cylinder is also plotted in Fig.4. Lack in capacity of the driving motor enabled the rotary test to be performed at the higher speed. The displacement of the shafts is shown against the rotary speed in Fig.16. This diagram was plotted based on a series of rotary tests conducted after each mass balancing. The success in the rotary test seemed brought about by the stabilized mechanical properties and high tensile modulus in the longitudinal direction of the circumferentially reinforced cylinder. Judging from the experimental results the B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites produced in the ambient atmosphere seemed promising.

5 CONCLUSIONS

B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites were consolidated under a diffusion bonding condition without using a vacuum bagging. Any autoclave was not used to make circumferentially reinforced metal matrix composite cylinders. Instead the technique which utilized the difference of thermal expansion of the inner and the outer dies to generate high consolidating pressure were used. From the experimental results the following conclusions were derived.

1. Consolidation in the ambient air could secure the mechanical properties of B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites.
2. The process which applied the difference of thermal expansion in the inner and the outer dies to generate high pressure necessary for consolidation gave the fruitful result in producing B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composite cylinders circumferentially reinforced.
3. Longitudinal tensile strength and modulus retained in coupon specimens were realized in tensile strength and modulus in the hoop direction of the composite cylinders.
4. Longitudinal tensile fatigue strength was relatively high compared with monotonic tensile strength for B- and SiC-aluminum alloy composites. This made a remarkable contrast to the fatigue characteristics of SUS304-AL6061 composite.
5. A rotor which utilized a B-AL6061 composite cylinder 200 mm in diameter, 300 mm in length and 0.5 mm thick survived the circumferential speed of 675 m/s (1070 rps).

REFERENCE

- (1) Crane, R.L. and Krukonis, V.J., "Strength and Fracture Properties of Silicon Carbide Filament" Ceramic Bulletin, Vol.54, No.2 (1975), pp.184-188.

Fig. 15. Vibrational wave form of rotor axles (1 div.=20 μ m).

Fig. 16. Relationship between axle displacement and rotational speed